

Fulminant Necrotizing Fasciitis Following Minor Trauma in a Young Adult: A Fatal Case of Delayed Treatment

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Introduction

Necrotizing fasciitis (NF) is a rapidly progressive soft tissue infection associated with high mortality, particularly when diagnosis and treatment are delayed. Group A Streptococcus is a common cause and may lead to streptococcal toxic shock syndrome. This case highlights the diagnostic challenges of early NF, where initial symptoms may be nonspecific.

Case Presentation

We report the case of a 29-year-old previously healthy male presenting initially with right thoraco-abdominal pain and cellulitis following minor trauma due to a fall from standing height. The patient declined hospitalization and was discharged. Within 24 hours, he returned in critical condition with septic shock, altered mental status, acute respiratory distress syndrome, and multiorgan failure. On clinical examination, extensive cellulitis with ecchymosis and bullae involving the right thoraco-abdominal region was observed. Laboratory investigations revealed a severe inflammatory response, pancytopenia, rhabdomyolysis, hepatic and renal dysfunction. The LRINEC score supported a high suspicion for necrotizing soft tissue infection in the context of the clinical presentation. CT demonstrated diffuse soft tissue infiltration with fluid collections along fascial planes (up to 26 mm), suggestive of a deep soft tissue infection. Emergency surgical exploration confirmed extensive necrotizing infection, requiring debridement. Despite intensive care management, including broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy (clindamycin, meropenem, and vancomycin) and surgical intervention, the patient developed refractory shock and died within 48 hours of admission. Microbiological analysis identified *Streptococcus pyogenes* as the causative pathogen.

Conclusion

Necrotizing fasciitis should be suspected in patients with severe pain disproportionate to clinical findings, even in the absence of clear skin changes. Delayed treatment significantly increases mortality, as emphasized in recent literature. Imaging modalities can support diagnosis, but early surgical exploration remains the gold standard. The LRINEC score and clinical suspicion are essential for early identification. Early diagnosis, prompt antibiotic therapy, and immediate surgical intervention are critical to improving survival.

Keywords

Necrotizing Fasciitis, *Streptococcus Pyogenes*, Delayed Treatment, Soft Tissue Infection, Surgical Emergency.